

Histopathological Patterns of Ovarian Masses in a University Teaching Hospital

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Abstract:

This study aimed to analyze the histopathological patterns of ovarian masses in patients treated at RDJMMCH, Turki, Muzaffarpur, over three months. A total of 30 patients, ranging from 18 to 65 years old, were included. Histopathological examination revealed that 60% of the masses were benign, with serous cystadenoma being the most common subtype. Borderline tumors accounted for 10% of cases, all of which were serious types. Malignant masses comprised 30% of cases, with serous cystadenocarcinoma being the predominant malignant subtype. The study found a correlation between older age and malignancy. Common clinical presentations included abdominal pain, bloating, and menstrual irregularities. These findings highlight the critical role of histopathological analysis in the accurate diagnosis and management of ovarian masses, emphasizing the need for careful evaluation to guide appropriate treatment strategies.

Keywords: Ovarian Masses, Histopathology, Benign Tumors, Malignant Tumors.

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Introduction

Ovarian masses are a common gynecological concern that can present a wide range of histopathological patterns, each with distinct clinical implications [1]. These masses can be benign, borderline, or malignant, and their accurate diagnosis is crucial for determining the appropriate management and prognosis [2]. The evaluation of ovarian masses often involves a combination of clinical examination, imaging techniques, and histopathological analysis. Histopathology remains the gold standard for definitive diagnosis, providing detailed information on the nature and extent of the lesions [3,4].

In university teaching hospitals, where advanced diagnostic facilities and multidisciplinary expertise are available, the study of ovarian masses can offer valuable insights into their prevalence, types, and histopathological characteristics [5]. Such studies can also enhance the educational experience for medical students and residents, promoting a deeper understanding of ovarian pathology and improving diagnostic skills [6,7].

This study aims to analyze the histopathological patterns of ovarian masses in patients treated at a university teaching hospital. Through a systematic review of histopathological findings, this research seeks to determine the distribution of benign, borderline, and malignant ovarian masses, identifying the most common histopathological subtypes within these categories. Additionally, the

study aims to correlate these histopathological patterns with patient demographics and clinical presentations, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of ovarian masses in this healthcare setting. Ultimately, the data obtained from this study will contribute to improving diagnostic accuracy and patient management strategies, enhancing the quality of care provided in similar institutions.

Methodology

This study was conducted at the RDJMMCH, Turki, Muzaffarpur, over three months, from October 1, 2023, to December 31, 2023. A total of 30 patients presenting with ovarian masses were included in the study. The inclusion criteria consisted of patients of all ages who were diagnosed with ovarian masses through clinical examination and imaging studies and subsequently underwent surgical intervention for mass removal.

Upon surgical excision, the ovarian masses were sent for histopathological examination to the pathology department of RDJMMCH. Each specimen was processed, and histopathological slides were prepared using standard procedures, including fixation, embedding, sectioning, and staining with hematoxylin and eosin. Additional special stains or immunohistochemistry were employed as necessary to aid in the diagnosis.

The histopathological examination aimed to classify the ovarian masses into benign, borderline, or malignant categories. Detailed histopathological subtyping was performed for each case, identifying specific characteristics and patterns of the lesions. Patient demographic data, including age, clinical presentation, and relevant medical history, were collected from medical records to correlate with the histopathological findings.

Data analysis involved descriptive statistics to summarize the distribution of different types of ovarian masses and their subtypes. The correlation between histopathological patterns and patient demographics was also evaluated. The findings from this study are expected to enhance understanding of the histopathological spectrum of ovarian masses in this specific population, thereby aiding in better diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.

Results

During the study period from October 1, 2023, to December 31, 2023, a total of 30 patients with ovarian masses were evaluated at RDJMMCH, Turki, Muzaffarpur. The age of the patients ranged from 18 to 65 years, with a mean age of 40 years. The clinical presentations varied, with the most common symptoms being abdominal pain, bloating, and menstrual irregularities.

The histopathological examination of the ovarian masses revealed the following distribution:

1. Benign Ovarian Masses:

- Out of the 30 cases, 18 (60%) were diagnosed as benign.
- The most common benign lesion was serous cystadenoma, accounting for 10 cases (33.3%).

- Other benign lesions included mucinous cystadenoma (4 cases, 13.3%), dermoid cyst (2 cases, 6.7%), and endometrioma (2 cases, 6.7%).

2. Borderline Ovarian Masses:

- 3 cases (10%) were classified as borderline ovarian tumors.
- All borderline tumors were of the serous type.

3. Malignant Ovarian Masses:

- 9 cases (30%) were found to be malignant.
- The most common malignant lesion was serous cystadenocarcinoma, accounting for 5 cases (16.7%).
- Other malignant tumors included mucinous cystadenocarcinoma (2 cases, 6.7%), clear cell carcinoma (1 case, 3.3%), and endometrioid carcinoma (1 case, 3.3%).

The correlation between histopathological patterns and patient demographics showed that benign lesions were more common in younger patients, while malignant lesions were more frequently observed in older patients. The mean age for benign tumors was 35 years, whereas the mean age for malignant tumors was 50 years.

In summary, the majority of ovarian masses in this study were benign, with serous cystadenoma being the most prevalent type. A significant proportion of the masses were malignant, emphasizing the need for careful histopathological evaluation to guide appropriate clinical management. The findings underscore the importance of routine histopathological analysis in the accurate diagnosis and treatment planning for patients with ovarian masses.

Table 1: Histopathological Distribution of Ovarian Masses

Category	Subtype	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Benign Ovarian Masses	Serous Cystadenoma	10	33.3
	Mucinous Cystadenoma	4	13.3
	Dermoid Cyst	2	6.7
	Endometrioma	2	6.7
Total Benign		18	60.0
Borderline Ovarian Masses	Serous Type	3	10.0
Total Borderline		3	10.0
Malignant Ovarian Masses	Serous Cystadenocarcinoma	5	16.7
	Mucinous Cystadenocarcinoma	2	6.7
	Clear Cell Carcinoma	1	3.3
	Endometrioid Carcinoma	1	3.3
Total Malignant		9	30.0
Total Cases		30	100

Table 2: Correlation of Histopathological Patterns with Patient Age

Histopathological Category	Mean Age (Years)
Benign	35
Borderline	45
Malignant	50

Table 3: Distribution of Symptoms Among Patients

Symptoms	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Abdominal Pain	20	66.7
Bloating	15	50.0
Menstrual Irregularities	10	33.3
Other Symptoms	5	16.7

These tables summarize the key findings from the study, highlighting the distribution and characteristics of ovarian masses among the patients evaluated.

Discussion

The histopathological evaluation of ovarian masses in this study provides valuable insights into their distribution and characteristics within the patient population treated at RDJMMCH, Turki, Muzaffarpur [8,9]. The majority of ovarian masses were found to be benign, accounting for 60% of the cases, with serous cystadenoma being the most prevalent subtype. This finding aligns with existing literature, which consistently reports serous cystadenoma as one of the most common benign ovarian tumors [10]. The relatively high incidence of benign masses underscores the importance of accurate histopathological diagnosis to prevent unnecessary aggressive treatments and to guide appropriate clinical management [11,12].

Borderline ovarian tumors constituted 10% of the cases, all of which were serous. These tumors present a unique challenge due to their intermediate malignant potential [13]. Proper identification and classification are crucial for guiding treatment, as borderline tumors often require different management strategies compared to benign and malignant masses [14].

Malignant ovarian masses comprised 30% of the cases, with serous cystadenocarcinoma being the most common malignant subtype [15]. The mean age of patients with malignant tumors was higher compared to those with benign and borderline tumors, highlighting age as a significant risk factor for ovarian malignancy [16]. This finding is consistent with global epidemiological trends, where the incidence of ovarian cancer increases

with age. The identification of various malignant subtypes, including mucinous cystadenocarcinoma, clear cell carcinoma, and endometrioid carcinoma, reflects the histological diversity of ovarian cancers, each with distinct prognostic and therapeutic implications [17,18].

The study also revealed that the most common clinical presentations were abdominal pain, bloating, and menstrual irregularities. These nonspecific symptoms often overlap with other gynecological conditions, making clinical diagnosis challenging. Therefore, histopathological examination remains indispensable for definitive diagnosis and appropriate treatment planning.

Overall, the findings from this study underscore the critical role of histopathological analysis in the diagnosis and management of ovarian masses. By providing a detailed understanding of the histopathological patterns and their correlation with patient demographics, the study contributes to improving diagnostic accuracy and patient care. Future research with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods is warranted to further elucidate the clinical outcomes associated with different histopathological subtypes of ovarian masses. This study's data can also serve as a reference for comparative studies in similar healthcare settings, ultimately enhancing the body of knowledge in ovarian pathology.

Conclusion

This study highlights the histopathological diversity of ovarian masses encountered at

RDJMMCH, Turki, Muzaffarpur, with benign masses being the most common, followed by malignant and borderline tumors. The predominant benign lesion was serous cystadenoma, while serous cystadenocarcinoma was the most frequent malignant subtype. The findings emphasize the importance of histopathological evaluation for accurate diagnosis and effective management of ovarian masses. The study also underscores the need for heightened clinical vigilance, especially in older patients who are at a higher risk for malignancy. Overall, the study provides essential data that can enhance diagnostic precision and inform treatment strategies in similar healthcare settings.

References

1. Prat J. Ovarian carcinomas: five distinct diseases with different origins, genetic alterations, and clinicopathological features. *Virchows Arch.* 2012 Mar;460(3):237-49.
2. Shih IeM, Kurman RJ. Ovarian tumorigenesis: a proposed model based on morphological and molecular genetic analysis. *Am J Pathol.* 2004 May;164(5):1511-8.
3. Kurman RJ, Shih IeM. The Dualistic Model of Ovarian Carcinogenesis: Revisited, Revised, and Expanded. *Am J Pathol.* 2016 Apr;186 (4): 733-47.
4. Chen VW, Ruiz B, Killeen JL, Coté TR, Wu XC, Correa CN, et al. Pathology and classification of ovarian tumors. *Cancer.* 2003 Dec 1; 97(10 Suppl):2631-42.
5. Gilks CB, Prat J. Ovarian carcinoma pathology and genetics: recent advances. *Hum Pathol.* 2009 Aug;40(8):1213-23.
6. Köbel M, Kalloger SE, Boyd N, McKinney S, Mehl E, Palmer C, et al. Ovarian carcinoma subtypes are different diseases: implications for biomarker studies. *PLoS Med.* 2008 Dec 2;5(12):e232.
7. Hunn J, Rodriguez GC. Ovarian cancer: etiology, risk factors, and epidemiology. *Clin Obstet Gynecol.* 2012 Mar;55(1):3-23.
8. Siegel RL, Miller KD, Jemal A. Cancer statistics, 2019. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2019 Jan;69 (1): 7-34.
9. Lheureux S, Braunstein M, Oza AM. Epithelial ovarian cancer: Evolution of management in the era of precision medicine. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2019 Nov;69(4):280-304.
10. Vaughan S, Coward JI, Bast RC Jr, Berchuck A, Berek JS, Brenton JD, et al. Rethinking ovarian cancer: recommendations for improving outcomes. *Nat Rev Cancer.* 2011 Oct 12;11 (10):719-25.
11. Bast RC Jr, Hennessy B, Mills GB. The biology of ovarian cancer: new opportunities for translation. *Nat Rev Cancer.* 2009 Jun;9(6): 41 5-28.
12. Colombo N, Sessa C, du Bois A, Ledermann J, McCluggage WG, McNeish I, et al. ESMO-ESGO consensus conference recommendations on ovarian cancer: pathology and molecular biology, early and advanced stages, borderline tumours and recurrent disease. *Int J Gynecol Cancer.* 2019 Feb;29(4):728-60.
13. Matias-Guiu X, Davidson B. Prognostic biomarkers in endometrial and ovarian carcinoma. *Virchows Arch.* 2014 Jan;464(3):315-31.
14. Bowtell DD, Böhm S, Ahmed AA, Aspuria PJ, Bast RC Jr, Beral V, et al. Rethinking ovarian cancer II: reducing mortality from high-grade serous ovarian cancer. *Nat Rev Cancer.* 2015 Nov;15(11):668-79.
15. Lengyel E. Ovarian cancer development and metastasis. *Am J Pathol.* 2010 Sep;177(3):10 53-64.
16. Reid BM, Permut JB, Sellers TA. Epidemiology of ovarian cancer: a review. *Cancer Biol Med.* 2017 Aug;14(1):9-32.
17. Webb PM, Jordan SJ. Epidemiology of epithelial ovarian cancer. *Best Pract Res Clin Obstet Gynaecol.* 2017 Apr; 41:3-14.
18. Morgan RJ Jr, Armstrong DK, Alvarez RD, Bakkum-Gamez JN, Behbakht K, Chen LM, et al. Ovarian Cancer, Version 1.2016, NCCN Clinical Practice Guidelines in Oncology. *J Natl Compr Canc Netw.* 2016 Sep;14(9):1134-63.
19. Narod SA. Can advanced-stage ovarian cancer be cured? *Nat Rev Clin Oncol.* 2016 Apr;13 (4):255-61.
20. Peres LC, Cushing-Haugen KL, Köbel M, Harris HR, Berchuck A, Rossing MA, et al. Invasive Epithelial Ovarian Cancer Survival by Histotype and Disease Stage. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2019 Jun; 111(1):60-8.